

Self-Assessment for Multi-Object Tracking Based on Subjective Logic

Thomas Griebel, Nikolas Dehler, Alexander Scheible,
Michael Buchholz, and Klaus Dietmayer

This paper has been accepted for presentation and publication at the 2024 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), June 02 - 05, 2024, Jeju Island, Republic of Korea. This is the accepted version of the paper, which has not been fully edited and the layout may differ from the original publication.

Citation information of the original publication:

T. Griebel, N. Dehler, A. Scheible, M. Buchholz and K. Dietmayer, "Self-Assessment for Multi-Object Tracking Based on Subjective Logic," 2024 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), Jeju Island, Korea, Republic of, 2024, pp. 1750-1757, doi: 10.1109/IV55156.2024.10588720.

Self-Assessment for Multi-Object Tracking Based on Subjective Logic

Thomas Griebel

Abstract—In automated driving, the safety and robustness of the overall system are among the most important key challenges today. To tackle these safety and robustness challenges, the monitoring and self-assessment of all modules in the automated system is necessary. Tracking surrounding objects as part of the environmental perception is a key module in automated systems. Thus, this work presents a novel overall concept and framework for self-assessment in multi-object tracking based on the subjective logic theory. The self-assessment concept is comprehensively discussed and evaluated by simulations and real-world data of the KITTI dataset, showing the relevance of this proposed method.

I. INTRODUCTION

The safety and robustness challenges are increasing with the development of more complex and advanced algorithms for automated driving systems. To address these challenges, the automotive industry has proposed functional safety standards such as the ISO 21448 safety of the intended functionality (SOTIF) [1]. One part of meeting this standard’s requirements is developing automated system self-assessment (SA) modules, such as for multi-object tracking (MOT).

In filter and tracking algorithms so far, mostly consistency tests for single criteria are performed, as, for example, the normalized innovation squared (NIS) [2]. Some extensions of the NIS to MOT exist as the multi-target generalized NIS (MGNIS) [3] or the approximate multi-target NIS (AMNIS) [4]. However, a holistic approach and framework of SA for MOT is still missing in the literature.

This paper presents a new concept for an SA module in MOT algorithms; see Fig. 1. Generally, the fulfillment of assumptions made by the tracking algorithm is essential to obtain reliable tracking results. Respectively, the SA of a MOT approach means that the correctness and validity of these assumptions are monitored. The proposed SA concept for general MOT systems is explained in detail and discussed such that all MOT system components are categorized and considered. After the general concept is introduced, a specific implementation of the SA module for the global nearest neighbor (GNN) algorithm [5] using subjective logic (SL) [6], a modern extension of probabilistic logic for

Parts of this research have been conducted as part of the EVENTS project and other parts as part of the PoDIUM project, which are both funded by the European Union under grant agreements No. 101069614 and No. 101069547, respectively. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

All authors are with the Institute of Measurement, Control and Microtechnology, Ulm University, Albert-Einstein-Allee 41, 89081 Ulm, Germany {firstname}.{lastname}@uni-ulm.de

Fig. 1. Our proposed unified self-assessment module for multi-sensor multi-object tracking obtains self-assessment scores for each sensor and each track.

reasoning under uncertainty, is presented. By developing the SA module for MOT algorithms, we continue our previous works [7]–[9], striving towards a unified and holistic SA framework for tracking algorithms. Our implementation is tested in simulations and on real-world data from the KITTI dataset [10] to demonstrate its suitability for online use in practice. Therefore, the proposed holistic SA concept for MOT is an essential step towards safety and robustness and meeting the SOTIF standard in automated driving.

Summarizing our work in this paper, we propose:

- a proposal of a general and holistic concept for SA in MOT in Section IV,
- an SL-based implementation of our SA concept using GNN association in Section V, and
- a comprehensive evaluation of the SA module in simulations and on real-world data from the KITTI dataset in Section VI.

II. RELATED WORK

Classical consistency tests in Kalman filtering, such as the NIS and the normalized estimation error squared (NEES), were introduced in [2]. While the NEES relies on ground truth (GT) data, which is unavailable during online operation, the NIS is considered a suitable SA measure that can be used online. Two multi-object extensions of the NIS, multi-target NIS (MNIS) and MGNIS, together with the generalized NIS (GNIS), have been established by the Mahler in [3]. These so-called divergence detectors can be used to monitor MOT systems online and do not rely on GT data. Reuter et al. extended this concept in [4] for the δ -GLMB filter

Fig. 2. Basic elements of an MOT system [5].

into a target-dependent $MGNIS_T$ and a clutter-dependent $MGNIS_C$. To compensate for the clutter dependence of the $MGNIS_T$, the AMNIS was proposed in the same work to obtain a multi-object divergence detector with similar characteristics to the single-target NIS. In addition, [11] proposed consistency checks, originating on the NIS, for a feature-based random-set Monte-Carlo localization. With this, several components of the measurement model for the localization in [11] are checked for consistency. However, research on monitoring and self-assessment of MOT systems has not been thoroughly explored, and many research questions remain open.

In previous works, we introduced an SA module for single-object tracking (SOT) in clutter using the SL theory [8]. This includes a self-assessing Kalman filter leveraging SL to model statistical uncertainty [7]. The extension to an SA framework for linear and nonlinear multi-sensor Kalman filters to monitor not only single-sensor SAs but also to assess the overall performance was presented in [9]. Moreover, in [8], we addressed the challenges of SA for SOT in clutter scenarios using the nearest neighbor association algorithm. These studies serve as a foundation for this work, which aims to build on the SA framework and extend it to the context of MOT. To the best of our knowledge, we are the first to propose a unified SA concept for MOT and, thus, the first implementation of such an SA module using SL.

III. FUNDAMENTALS

This section introduces the basics of MOT algorithms, the foundations of the SL theory, and the general SA procedure based on SL.

A. Multi-Object Tracking

Our work is based on MOT algorithms that use the multi-instance Kalman filter approach [12], where each track is treated independently by having its own individual filter. The algorithm can be divided into four elements: Filtering and prediction, gating, association, and update and track maintenance [5]. The recursive tracking process is illustrated in Fig. 2. The first step is the *filtering and prediction* on the states of the tracks. *Gating* is applied to reduce unlikely hypotheses and exclude unlikely measurements for the following measurement-to-track *association*. With the association hypotheses, the *update* of the filtering algorithm is performed to obtain the states of the tracked objects for the next time step. When objects enter or leave the sensor's field of view (FoV), the *track maintenance* step is used by

deleting low-probability tracks or generating new ones to handle the phenomena of object birth and death. After that, a new prediction is made on the latest states to complete the recursive algorithm.

1) *Kalman Filtering*: The Kalman filter [13] is the foundation of most of the tracking algorithms. It is an optimal estimator for Bayesian estimation problems for the state $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ using the measurements $\mathbf{z}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ assuming linear systems with zero-mean white Gaussian noise sequences. The Kalman filter recursion is given by

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} = \mathbf{F}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k, \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k+1|k} = \mathbf{F}_k \mathbf{P}_k \mathbf{F}_k^T + \mathbf{Q}_k, \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{z}}_{k+1|k} = \mathbf{H}_{k+1} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k}, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{k+1} = \mathbf{H}_{k+1} \mathbf{P}_{k+1|k} \mathbf{H}_{k+1}^T + \mathbf{R}_{k+1}, \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{K}_{k+1} = \mathbf{P}_{k+1|k} \mathbf{H}_{k+1}^T \mathbf{S}_{k+1}^{-1} \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} + \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \gamma_{k+1}, \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{k+1} = \mathbf{P}_{k+1|k} + \mathbf{K}_{k+1} \mathbf{S}_{k+1} \mathbf{K}_{k+1}^T, \quad (7)$$

with the process and measurement matrix $\mathbf{F}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{H}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, and the state and measurement prediction $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{k+1|k} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\hat{\mathbf{z}}_{k+1|k} \in \mathbb{R}^m$. In addition, $\mathbf{Q}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ are the covariance matrices of the process and measurement noise $\mathbf{v}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\mathbf{w}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$. Moreover, $\mathbf{P}_{k+1|k}$, $\mathbf{P}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, and $\mathbf{S}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ are the covariance matrices of the predicted and estimated state and the innovation, respectively. $\mathbf{K}_{k+1} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ denotes the Kalman gain. Here, k is the time step index for the underlying constant sample time. Within the update step, the measurement or *pre-fit* residual γ_{k+1} is defined by

$$\gamma_{k+1} := \mathbf{z}_{k+1} - \hat{\mathbf{z}}_{k+1|k}. \quad (8)$$

Similar to the pre-fit residual, the *post-fit* residual $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k$ can be defined as [14]

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_k := \mathbf{z}_k - \mathbf{H}_k \hat{\mathbf{x}}_k. \quad (9)$$

The covariance for the post-fit residual is given by

$$\mathbf{G}_k = \mathbf{R}_k - \mathbf{H}_k \mathbf{P}_k \mathbf{H}_k^T. \quad (10)$$

A multi-sensor system comprises several sensors that aim to track the same object. There are two main approaches for synchronized data collection systems [15]: The parallel and the sequential filter. In this work, we utilize a multi-sensor approach with sequential updates, which enables the SA of individual sensors separately. We assume synchronous data collection, meaning that all sensors obtain measurements at the exact same time.

2) *Statistical Assumptions in Tracking Systems*: Most object tracking techniques are model-based and rely on several statistical assumptions [5]. Both the motion and measurement models are assumed to be linear. Additionally, zero mean, white Gaussian noise sequences are assumed for linear systems that use Gaussian filtering. To account for the uncertainty associated with the sensor's ability to detect an object, a detection probability denoted as p_D is introduced. Therefore, detections are missed with a probability $1 - p_D$,

and the sensor's object detection process follows a Bernoulli distribution. Furthermore, the number of clutter measurements $m_k^c \in \mathbb{N}_0$ is assumed to follow a Poisson distribution with the expected number $\bar{\lambda}_c \in (0, \infty)$, i.e., $m_k^c \sim \text{Poi}(\bar{\lambda}_c)$. The spatial distribution $\lambda_c(\mathbf{z})$ of the clutter measurements is assumed to be uniform.

3) *Global Nearest Neighbor Data Association*: Data association is the process of correctly associating measurements with objects. The association becomes more complex when multiple objects are introduced into the system. To reduce computational time, gating is used after the prediction step to eliminate unlikely hypotheses. A gate is set around the predicted measurement, and only measurements within the gate are considered for association. We use a GNN approach [5] for the data association algorithm. It evaluates all valid object-to-measurement pairings and selects the one with the lowest statistical distance, considering a measurement can only be associated with one object. The distance of each measurement $\mathbf{z}_{j,k}$ to object state $\mathbf{x}_{i,k}$ association can be described using the normalized statistical distance

$$d_{ij,k}^2 = \gamma_{ij,k}^T \mathbf{S}_{ij,k}^{-1} \gamma_{ij,k}, \quad (11)$$

where $\gamma_{ij,k}$ represents the pre-fit residual for each object $i \in [1, \dots, o]$ with respect to each measurement $j \in [1, \dots, \tilde{m}]$, where o is the number of objects and \tilde{m} is the number of measurements. The measure of similarity for the GNN association algorithm is the generalized statistical distance

$$d_{Gij,k} = d_{ij,k}^2 + \ln \|\mathbf{S}_{i,k}\|. \quad (12)$$

4) *Track Maintenance*: Track maintenance algorithms model the phenomena of object birth and death. Object birth occurs when objects enter the sensor's FoV, and object death occurs when they leave it. We use a two-staged cascaded logic [5] as a track initiation algorithm to account for the effect of object birth. A common approach for object death is a track deletion algorithm based on the absence of detections or the state covariance matrix surpassing a certain threshold [5]. We decided on the covariance-based track deletion as the requirements are more flexible.

B. Subjective Logic

This section presents the SL theory's basics, based on [6]. SL can explicitly model the statistical uncertainty. The key components of SL are the so-called opinions. A multinomial opinion ω_X about a discrete random variable X represents information about the belief, uncertainty, and base rate.

Definition 1 (Multinomial Opinion). *Let $X \in \mathbb{X}$ be a random variable with cardinality $W = |\mathbb{X}| \geq 2$. Then, a multinomial opinion is defined as $\omega_X = (\mathbf{b}_X, u_X, \mathbf{a}_X)$ with*

$$\mathbf{b}_X(x) : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad 1 = u_X + \sum_{x \in \mathbb{X}} \mathbf{b}_X(x), \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_X(x) : \mathbb{X} \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad 1 = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{X}} \mathbf{a}_X(x). \quad (14)$$

The belief mass distribution \mathbf{b}_X represents the belief in each event, the uncertainty mass $u_X \in [0, 1]$ models the lack

of evidence, and the base rate distribution \mathbf{a}_X is the prior probability for each event.

The projected probability can be used to project a multinomial opinion to a classical probability distribution by

$$\mathbf{P}_X(x) = \mathbf{b}_X(x) + \mathbf{a}_X(x)u_X, \quad \forall x \in \mathbb{X}. \quad (15)$$

In the classical probability space, the projected probability is equal to the expected outcome of the opinion.

In SL, there are multiple operators to fuse and merge opinions. For example, the cumulative belief fusion (CBF) and the averaging belief fusion (ABF) [6] can be used for different tasks and applications. The availability of multiple fusion operators is one of the advantages of SL when comparing, for example, to the Dempster-Shafer theory. For more details about the fusion operator and when to use which, see [6]. In addition, two opinions about the same variable X can also be compared, and the distance can be measured by the degree of conflict (DC) [6].

Definition 2 (Degree of Conflict). *Consider two multinomial opinions ω_X^A and ω_X^B of source A and B over $X \in \mathbb{X}$. The degree of conflict DC $(\omega_X^A, \omega_X^B) \in [0, 1]$ between two opinions is computed by*

$$\text{DC}(\omega_X^A, \omega_X^B) = \text{PD}(\omega_X^A, \omega_X^B) \cdot \text{CC}(\omega_X^A, \omega_X^B), \quad (16)$$

using the projected distance $\text{PD}(\omega_X^A, \omega_X^B) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{x \in \mathbb{X}} |\mathbf{P}_X^A(x) - \mathbf{P}_X^B(x)| \in [0, 1]$ and the conjunctive certainty $\text{CC}(\omega_X^A, \omega_X^B) = (1 - u_X^A)(1 - u_X^B) \in [0, 1]$.

In general, a small DC means the opinions are similar, whereas a large DC means that they differ. Further details of SL can be found in [6].

C. Subjective Logic-Based Self-Assessment Procedure

The basic SL-based SA procedure is mainly based on [7], [8]. In the general algorithm, a multinomial opinion ω_X^z based on the incoming measurements \mathbf{z} is generated in each time step. With this opinion, the correctness of the Kalman filter's assumptions is modeled regarding the incoming measurements. To build up such an opinion, the underlying domain of interest \mathbb{X} is discretized such that the events $x \in \mathbb{X}$ are obtained. For further information on this step, refer to [7], [8]. After obtained this opinion ω_X^z regarding the current measurement, the short-term and long-term opinions ω_X^{st} and ω_X^{lt} are taken into account. Opinion ω_X^{st} represents a short-term and ω_X^{lt} a long-term memory about the collected evidence of the assumption fulfillment. Then, ω_X^{st} is updated and fused with ω_X^z by using the CBF operator in each time step. After a fixed short-term window of $n_{\text{st}} \in \mathbb{N}$ evidence is collected, a short-term long-term comparison is performed using the DC (16) between ω_X^{st} and ω_X^{lt} . Suppose the DC exceeds a derived confidence-based threshold using [8], indicating a conflict between short- and long-term opinion. In that case, ω_X^{lt} gets overwritten with ω_X^{st} , and the latter one gets reset. In the other case of consistency between these two memories, i.e., the DC is

below a threshold, the CBF operator is used to fuse the short- and long-term opinion to obtain the resulting final opinion

$$\omega_X = (\mathbf{b}_X, u_X, \mathbf{a}_X). \quad (17)$$

Then, based on the resulting opinion ω_X and a related reference opinion ω_X^{ref} , the SA scores can be obtained. The reference opinion ω_X^{ref} represents the initial Kalman filter assumptions, which aim to be checked. To make this comparison, the DC between these two opinions is used as

$$\delta = \text{DC}(\omega_X, \omega_X^{\text{ref}}). \quad (18)$$

Then, the SA output is obtained in terms of

$$(\delta, u_X, \eta). \quad (19)$$

Here, $\delta \in [0, 1]$ is the SA score, $u_X \in [0, 1]$ is the associated uncertainty of the SA score, and $\eta \in [0, 1]$ the corresponding confidence-level threshold. In [8], the threshold η is formulated and derived from the opinion ω_X and a specific significance level $\alpha \in [0, 1]$. The threshold η denotes a limit for the SA score δ regarding a given significance level α such that exceeding the threshold η means that the filter assumptions made are violated and the violation is reported.

IV. SELF-ASSESSMENT MODULE FOR MULTI-OBJECT TRACKING

This section presents the general concept of an SA module for MOT. The SA module assesses different MOT components with respect to their underlying statistical assumptions. The goal is to assess all aspects of the tracking systems. We propose a sensor- and track-wise categorizing of all assessed elements and statistical assumptions of the tracking system.

The categorization outlined below includes clutter, detection probability, noise assumptions, and the data association algorithm. Note that we chose not to assess the track maintenance algorithms used. Tentative tracks are subject to the same algorithms as confirmed tracks, meaning that the filter algorithms directly affect the performance of the track maintenance, which is already assessed with the established module itself. In addition, the algorithms used for track maintenance are often empirical approaches [5] with fewer statistical assumptions. Thus, this component is often not suitable for SA system monitoring.

1) *Clutter Assumption*: The characteristics of clutter are mainly sensor-specific. For example, the sensor's FoV or the weather sensitivity affect the amount of clutter measurements of a sensor. The clutter assumption, which is typically modeled by a Poisson-distributed clutter rate $m_k^c \sim \text{Poi}(\lambda_c)$ and a uniform spatial distribution $\lambda_c(\mathbf{z})$, is generally modeled for each sensor. Thus, the assessment of the clutter assumption is naturally categorized per sensor.

2) *Detection Probability*: The ability of a sensor to measure an object is also sensor-specific. This directly affects the detection probability p_D . However, the detection probability is also related to the different tracks. Object positioning, motion, orientation, and size influence the probability of detection. Hence, we have two different categorizations for the detection probability. First, per sensor and then per

Fig. 3. Overview of our implemented SA module for MOT.

track, to assess each sensor's detection probability for the tracks. Second, per track over all sensors, to make a general statement about the system's detection capability.

3) *Noise Assumptions*: The assumptions regarding noise can be divided into two categories: Process noise, which depends on the objects' specific motion dynamics, and measurement noise, which depends on the specific sensors. Although a direct online evaluation of the process and measurement model may not appear feasible, it is possible to consider several aspects that these models influence.

a) *Pre-Fit Residual*: The prediction and the measurement directly affect the pre-fit residual γ_{k+1} . The prediction is obtained through the motion model and its assumed process noise, which depends on the tracks. In contrast, the sensor characteristics directly impact the measurements. As a result, we have chosen to categorize the pre-fit residual per sensor and then per track.

b) *Post-Fit Residual*: The post-fit residual μ_k is calculated after the sequential update and is influenced by all sensors that are taken into account. However, the track dependency remains the same as the pre-fit residual with the updated predicted state. Thus, categorizing the post-fit residual over all sensors and for each track is reasonable.

4) *Data Association*: Data association ambiguity presents a challenging issue for tracking systems as it can lead to track divergence. Due to the significance of this aspect, it is essential to assess the ambiguity of the association, especially for association algorithms that make hard decisions, such as the GNN. Data association is responsible for identifying suitable pairings between all measurements of each sensor and the existing tracks. In our SA module, we refer to this as the association situation. The measurements highly influence the association algorithm, whether they are clutter or object measurements. Therefore, we categorize the assessment of the association situation per sensor.

V. GLOBAL NEAREST NEIGHBOR IMPLEMENTATION USING SUBJECTIVE LOGIC

This section presents the implementation of our SA concept for the GNN algorithm using SL. The implemented SA module is illustrated in Fig. 3. It consists of SA modules for each sensor, called *SA Sensor*, and an SA module for general assessment of all sensors, called *SA Post*. Because the GNN makes hard association decisions, such that associated

measurements can clearly be assigned to specific tracks, it is possible to set up these different types of SA modules. The assessment is performed using SL-based opinions.

1) *SA Sensor Module*: According to the categorization provided in the previous section, the SA Sensor Module includes a sensor-specific assessment of the clutter assumption in the form of the clutter opinion and an assessment of the association situation in the form of the association situation opinion. The detection probability is assessed using the detection opinion. To evaluate the noise assumptions, the pre-fit and the gate opinion are implemented. Here, the gate opinion assesses the measurement distribution within the gate. Note that the pre-fit, the gate, and the detection opinions evaluate different aspects of the individual tracks and sensors such that in the SA Sensor Module, there are instances initiated of these opinions for each track. Moreover, all the SA components except the association situation use the general SA procedure described in Section III-C after obtaining the evidence-based and reference opinions. This means they all output the SA scores in the form of (19).

a) *Clutter Opinion*: The construction of the clutter opinion $\omega_{X,\text{clutter}}$ is based on [8] with the goal to validate the assumed Poisson distributed clutter rate m_k^c modeled by the reference $\omega_{X,\text{clutter}}^{\text{ref}}$. For more details, please refer to [8].

b) *Association Situation Opinion*: The association situation opinion is also constructed for each sensor. The entropy, as defined in information theory [16], is used as an indicator of the data association ambiguity, as in [17]. Given a probabilistic assignment matrix

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} p^{(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{z}_1)} & p^{(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{z}_2)} & \dots & p^{(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{z}_m)} \\ p^{(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{z}_1)} & p^{(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{z}_2)} & \dots & p^{(\mathbf{x}_2, \mathbf{z}_m)} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ p^{(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{z}_1)} & p^{(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{z}_2)} & \dots & p^{(\mathbf{x}_n, \mathbf{z}_m)} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (20)$$

where $p^{(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)}$ denotes the probability of assigning object \mathbf{x}_i to measurement \mathbf{z}_j , $i \in [1, n]$, $j \in [1, m]$, with n the number of objects and m the number of measurements. We now use the probabilistic assignment matrix to calculate the entropy of a GNN association situation as follows

$$H(\mathbf{A}) = - \sum_i^n \sum_j^m p^{(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)} \log \left(p^{(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)} \right), \quad (21)$$

if $p^{(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)} \neq 0$. The entries of \mathbf{A} with $p^{(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{z}_j)} = 0$ for measurements outside the gating region will not be considered. To ensure comparability over time, it is necessary to normalize the entropy to a range of $[0, 1]$ by the number of objects and measurements, i.e.,

$$H_{\text{norm}} = \sum_i \frac{H(P_{\mathbf{x}_i})}{n \log(m_i)}, \quad (22)$$

where m_i represents the number of measurements within the gate of object \mathbf{x}_i . The entropy of the row vector corresponding to track \mathbf{x}_i is denoted by $H(P_{\mathbf{x}_i})$. In the case of a missed detection, the entropy of the object-corresponding row is set to $\frac{H(P_{\mathbf{x}_i})}{\log(m_i)} = 0$, indicating a completely unambiguous association situation. In contrast, if every measurement within the

gate has the same probability, the resulting entropy will be $\frac{H(P_{\mathbf{x}_i})}{\log(m_i)} = 1$, indicating a complete ambiguous association situation. The resulting score can then be averaged over a short sliding window to output the association situation measure. Note that, unlike the other components, this SA component does not provide an output in the form of (19).

c) *Pre-Fit, Gate, and Detection Opinions*: The pre-fit, gate, and detection opinions $\omega_{X,\text{pre-fit}}$, $\omega_{X,\text{gate}}$, $\omega_{X,\text{det}}$ are constructed in the same way as described in [8]. It is important to note that the overall opinion has been renamed to pre-fit, the measurement opinion to gate, and the association opinion to detection to better align with the assessed assumptions. This results in the reference opinions $\omega_{X,\text{pre-fit}}^{\text{ref}}$, $\omega_{X,\text{gate}}^{\text{ref}}$, and $\omega_{X,\text{det}}^{\text{ref}}$ for the validation of the assumptions. The basis of the reference opinions is the reference distribution of the transformed measurement likelihood, which is derived in [8]. This can be used here because of the possible track-dependent consideration of the GNN. The pre-fit opinion focuses on the monitoring of the whole transformed measurement likelihood. The gate opinion, however, focuses only on the case of an association and its resulting distribution. And the detection opinion on the basic event of an association or a missed detection. Note that the same measurement prediction obtained in the filter recursion is used for each sensor along with its individual measurements to form the pre-fit residuals. The multi-sensor framework allows for comparing different SAs for each sensor, enabling the identification of individual flaws in each sensor.

2) *SA Post Module*: The SA Post Module includes the post-fit, post-gate, and post-detection opinions similar to the pre-fit residual-based opinions. It is conducted after the sequential update to provide a comprehensive online evaluation of the GNN performance across all sensors. The opinions are constructed based on the a-posteriori state distribution and incorporate the information from all sensors.

a) *Post-Fit Opinion*: The purpose of the post-fit opinion $\omega_{X,\text{post-fit}}$ is to provide an overall SA of the multi-sensor tracking. The reference opinion $\omega_{X,\text{post-fit}}^{\text{ref}}$ is basically the same as the reference of the pre-fit opinion $\omega_{X,\text{pre-fit}}^{\text{ref}}$. The post-fit opinion is constructed for each track to its associated measurements of each sensor. The evidence is accumulated over the post-fit residuals of all sensors.

b) *Post-Gate Opinion*: The post-gate opinion $\omega_{X,\text{post-gate}}$ follows the same construction as the gate opinion, except the gate is built around the a-posteriori state after the sequential update. It represents the spatial uncertainties of the associated measurements towards the a-posteriori state. The post-gate opinion assesses the individual performance of each track by specifically assessing the assumed measurement noise over all sensors.

c) *Post-Detection Opinion*: The purpose of the post-detection opinion $\omega_{X,\text{post-det}}$ is to provide a global SA of the detection probability for each specific track, considering all sensors combined. It is constructed analogously to $\omega_{X,\text{det}}$. The post-detection opinion allows us to identify tracks with poor detection performance across all sensors.

Fig. 4. Ground truth trajectories of the objects in the three considered scenarios. The start and end points are marked by circles and triangles, respectively. Track 1 is common to all three association scenarios, while track 2 differs for each scenario, resulting in different association situations.

VI. EXPERIMENTS

In this section, we evaluate our proposed SA module for MOT applications. First, three association scenarios are investigated and assessed using the association situation opinion. Second, a challenging simulation scenario with multiple disturbances is assessed using the SA module. Third, our proposed method is evaluated on real-world KITTI data for 3D tracking scenarios.

A. Simulations

Our simulations consider a multi-sensor system consisting of three sensors, measuring multiple objects in two dimensions $(x, y) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. For evaluating our SA procedure, the assumptions made about all three sensors in the GNN tracking algorithm are initially assumed to be identical to the ground truth (GT) modeled assumptions such that our SA can initially state that everything works well as expected. In addition, the nearly constant velocity (CV) model [2] is used, which results in a linear scenario. All results are averaged values from 200 Monte Carlo runs.

1) *Association Scenario*: First, the proposed association situation opinion is investigated using three scenarios shown in Fig. 4. The trajectory of track 1 is the same for all three scenarios. However, track 2 varies between very close and distant parallel tracks and the intersection or crossing with track 1. This results in an ambiguous, crossing, and unambiguous association scenario. The corresponding results of the association situation component in the SA module are shown in Fig. 5. The association situation SA obtains a score between zero and one, where one means an ambiguous and zero an unambiguous association situation. The SA measures correctly monitor these unambiguities over time.

2) *Disturbance Scenario*: The next simulation scenario consists of two tracks in which trajectories are sampled randomly. This scenario, however, includes multiple disturbances in the assumptions of the measurement noise, the clutter rate, and the detection probability of sensor 1. These disturbances are switched on one after the other during time steps 100–200, 300–400, and 500–600. The results of the

Fig. 5. The results of the association situation (asso. sit.) SA measures from one sensor in the different association scenarios. The SA measures correctly monitor the different ambiguities of the association scenarios.

full SA Sensor Modules for all three sensors compared with the time-averaged MNIS are plotted in Fig. 6. The sensor 1 SA measures of the proposed SA module correctly monitor the disturbances in the corresponding SA components. These disturbances are reported by the SA measures exceeding the thresholds. The disturbance in the measurement noise can be seen in the pre-fit opinion, the clutter rate disturbance in the clutter opinion, and the detection probability disturbance in the pre-fit and detection opinions. In contrast, the MNIS comparison measure only detects the measurement noise disturbance in sensor 1. However, it also shows some violations for sensors 2 and 3, which are false. In addition, the SL-based SA module can clearly distinguish the various aspects, which is not possible with the MNIS.

The full SA Post module results consisting of the SA measures for track 1 and 2 are visualized in Fig. 7. The corresponding SA measures report small violations in the post-fit and detection opinions due to sensor 1 disturbances. These overall SA Post results can also be compared to the GT-based evaluation metric OSPA [18] shown in Fig. 8. The OSPA mainly shows an increase in the first disturbance of the measurement noise of sensor 1. However, the other aspects can also highly influence the evaluation measure in general.

B. Application to Real-World KITTI Data

Moreover, we applied our developed SA module to real-world tracking scenarios using the KITTI 3D tracking dataset [10]. Our focus is on performing the GNN tracking algorithm on lidar sensor data. Here, we exemplarily evaluate our SA module on the training sequences 4 and 10 of the 3D object tracking benchmark. As the input of our tracking system, 3D detection data are obtained using the detections from [19]. Hence, the tracking algorithm is performed using the 3D detection data and our SA module.

1) *Association Situation*: First, the association situation opinion is evaluated in Fig. 9 for the two KITTI sequences 4 and 10. The first track is initiated in time step 2 in both sequences. Thus, the association situation SA measure for the lidar detections starts at this time step. Sequence 4 has many cars parked close to the street, leading to many ambiguous association situations. This is also displayed in our SA measure association situation. In contrast, sequence

Fig. 6. The full SA Sensor Modules results for all three sensors are shown and compared to the time-averaged MNIS. Sensor 1 is disturbed in its measurement noise, clutter rate, and detection probability assumptions, whereas sensors 2 and 3 work properly. Red shadows indicate these disturbances, which are monitored by the SA module. A violation is reported when the SA measures exceed the thresholds or the confidence interval (conf. int.).

Fig. 7. The full SA Post Module results are shown to monitor the overall tracking performance. Because the sensor 1 disturbances influence both tracks, both SA measures increase, leading to small violation reports in the post-fit and post-detection opinions. Red shadows indicate these disturbances.

Fig. 8. The GT-based evaluation results of the OSPA show some increases during the sensor 1 disturbances, which are indicated by red shadows.

Fig. 9. Association situation (asso. sit.) results of the lidar detections from the KITTI dataset evaluated on sequences 4 and 10.

10 is mostly a clear scenario where the ego vehicle follows another vehicle, which is indicated by a consistently high association situation SA measure.

2) *SA Module for Sequence 10*: Moreover, our SA module applied to the KITTI sequence 10 is shown in Fig. 10. The SL-based SA measures indicate that the monitored tracking assumptions are fulfilled and everything works smoothly. This is, in fact, the case for the selected leading track, which is detected in every time step, resulting in good SA detection results. In contrast, the MNIS considers all tracks, which leads to some increases and violations. The clutter SA

measure also indicates that the assumptions are met.

3) *Initiation of a False-Positive Track*: A false-positive track may be mistakenly initiated when consecutive clutter measurements fall within the gating distance of each other. False-positive tracks are a challenge in MOT because they can cause the autonomous system to react in an undesirable way. In sequence 10 of the KITTI dataset, false-positive tracks are generated within the tracking. For example, Fig. 11 illustrates such a track's detection and gate opinion. In fact, our proposed SA module is capable of distinguishing between false-positive tracks and true object-generated

Fig. 10. The results of SA measures from the SA Sensor Module for sequence 10 of the KITTI tracking dataset. The clutter and detection opinions are visualized and compared to the single time step MNIS. The detection SA measure is from a specific track, the leading vehicle in this sequence, which is initiated at time step 18. The MNIS, in contrast, takes all tracks into account.

Fig. 11. SA measures of a false-positive initiated track in sequence 10 of the KITTI tracking dataset. The false-positive track can be identified by our SA module before the deleter reacts.

tracks. Firstly, the detection opinion exceeds the threshold before the deletion algorithm catches the track. Secondly, the uncertainty of the gate opinion remains high due to missed detections. In the case of a missed detection, a vacuous opinion is used as evidence for the gate opinion with an uncertainty of one. This information can possibly be used to improve the reliability of the track maintenance algorithms and the tracking system.

VII. CONCLUSION

To conclude, this work proposed the first unified SA concept and implementation for MOT algorithms. The monitoring of several components in the MOT systems, as demonstrated in the experiments, shows reliable and promising results to make the automated driving systems safer. Based on the evaluation results, the presented holistic SA module can be an initial step in fulfilling the SOTIF standard requirements for MOT in automated driving.

In future work, an overall SA layer should be introduced on top of the SA module that summarizes and fuses the critical SA statements into some overall SA measures. The proposed SA concept is formulated in a generalized way such that it should be applicable to various MOT approaches. Moreover, on the way to making automated driving even more robust, the proposed SA approach should be extensively tested and enhanced during real-world applications.

REFERENCES

- [1] "ISO/PAS 21448: Road vehicles - Safety of the intended functionality," *International Organization for Standardization*, 2019.
- [2] Y. Bar-Shalom, X. R. Li, and T. Kirubarajan, *Estimation with applications to tracking and navigation: theory algorithms and software*. John Wiley & Sons, 2001.
- [3] R. Mahler, "Divergence detectors for multitarget tracking algorithms," in *Signal Processing, Sensor Fusion, and Target Recognition XXII*, vol. 8745. SPIE, 2013.
- [4] S. Reuter, B.-T. Vo, B. Wilking, D. Meissner, and K. Dietmayer, "Divergence detectors for the δ -generalized labeled multi-Bernoulli filter," in *2013 Workshop on Sensor Data Fusion: Trends, Solutions, Applications (SDF)*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 1–6.
- [5] S. S. Blackman and R. Popoli, *Design and analysis of modern tracking systems*. Artech House, 1999.
- [6] A. Jøsang, *Subjective Logic: A formalism for reasoning under uncertainty*. Springer International Publishing, 2016.
- [7] T. Griebel, J. Müller, M. Buchholz, and K. Dietmayer, "Kalman filter meets subjective logic: A self-assessing Kalman filter using subjective logic," in *2020 IEEE 23rd International Conference on Information Fusion (FUSION)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–8.
- [8] T. Griebel, J. Müller, P. Geisler, C. Hermann, M. Herrmann, M. Buchholz, and K. Dietmayer, "Self-assessment for single-object tracking in clutter using subjective logic," in *2022 25th International Conference on Information Fusion (FUSION)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8.
- [9] T. Griebel, J. Heinzler, M. Buchholz, and K. Dietmayer, "Online performance assessment of multi-sensor Kalman filters based on subjective logic," in *2023 26th International Conference on Information Fusion (FUSION)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–8.
- [10] A. Geiger, P. Lenz, and R. Urtasun, "Are we ready for autonomous driving? The KITTI vision benchmark suite," in *2012 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*. IEEE, 2012.
- [11] M. Stübler, S. Reuter, and K. Dietmayer, "Consistency of feature-based random-set Monte-Carlo localization," in *2017 European Conference on Mobile Robots (ECMR)*, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [12] S. Reuter, "Multi-object tracking using random finite sets," Ph.D. dissertation, Ulm University, 2014.
- [13] R. E. Kalman, "A new approach to linear filtering and prediction problems," *Transactions of the ASME - Journal of Basic Engineering*, vol. 82, no. 1, pp. 35–45, 1960.
- [14] L. Zhang, D. Sidoti, A. Bienkowski, K. R. Pattipati, Y. Bar-Shalom, and D. L. Kleinman, "On the identification of noise covariances and adaptive Kalman filtering: A new look at a 50 year-old problem," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 59 362–59 388, 2020.
- [15] D. Willner, C. B. Chang, and K. P. Dunn, "Kalman filter algorithms for a multi-sensor system," in *1976 IEEE Conference on Decision and Control including the 15th Symposium on Adaptive Processes*, 1976, pp. 570–574.
- [16] C. E. Shannon, "A mathematical theory of communication," *The Bell System Technical Journal*, vol. 27, pp. 379–423, 1948.
- [17] A. Danzer, S. Reuter, and K. Dietmayer, "The adaptive labeled multi-Bernoulli filter," in *2016 19th International Conference on Information Fusion (FUSION)*, 2016, pp. 1531–1538.
- [18] D. Schuhmacher, B.-T. Vo, and B.-N. Vo, "A consistent metric for performance evaluation of multi-object filters," *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, vol. 56, no. 8, pp. 3447–3457, 2008.
- [19] X. Weng, J. Wang, D. Held, and K. Kitani, "Ab3dmt: A baseline for 3d multi-object tracking and new evaluation metrics," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2008.08063*, 2020.